

A Computational Model for Agents in a Social Context: An Approach based on Theory of Mind

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Abstract. Socialization should be considered in any Ambient Intelligent system (AmI) where several persons interact, and specially in mental health-oriented ones. A crucial aspect of human social interaction and understanding is the Theory of Mind (ToM), which involves the ability to comprehend and predict the mental state of others, being critical for successful social functioning. The hypothesis of this paper is that the use of ToM to develop Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) to support AmI will enable modeling and reasoning about the mind of the people interacting in the system, making the agent that embodies a person more effective, efficient and social-capable than agents lacking such capacity. This paper presents a computational model based on ToM to support the reasoning and decision-making of socio-cognitive agents. The model applies the fundamental principles of ToM and Belief-Desire-Intention (BDI) agent model to develop a multi-agent system adaptable to real-world scenarios. The case study focuses on School Bullying, for which social theories validate the behavior of the proposed socio-cognitive agents. The results provide a suitable framework integrating advanced technologies with the necessary AI capabilities for the development of social-aware Ambient Intelligent systems.

Keywords: social agents · social context · theory of mind · BDI

1 Introduction

Ambient Intelligent systems (AmI) that facilitate human social interaction and understanding have gained significant attention in recent years [8]. These systems aim to create intelligent environments that seamlessly integrate technology with the physical surroundings, enabling enhanced communication, social interaction, and information exchange among individuals. One crucial aspect of successful functioning of social interaction is the ToM, which enables individuals to comprehend and predict the mental states of others [9]. The importance of ToM extends across various domains, including psychology and education. In psychology settings, ToM plays a crucial role in understanding social cognition, empathy, and ToM development in individuals across different age groups. Moreover, in the educational field, the ability to interpret and anticipate the mental

states of students and teachers is essential for fostering effective communication, personalized learning experiences, and collaborative problem-solving.

This paper presents a computational model based on ToM and the BDI agent model, aiming to develop a multi-agent system adaptable to real-world scenarios. The hypothesis driving this research is that incorporating ToM into MAS within a BDI approach can enhance the modeling and reasoning capabilities of socio-cognitive agents, resulting in more effective and socially capable agents. By leveraging the fundamental principles of ToM, which involve understanding others’ beliefs, desires, and intentions, the proposed model enables agents to reason and make informed decisions in complex social contexts. The integration of ToM with the BDI approach provides a promising avenue for advancing the capabilities of socio-cognitive agents, fostering more natural and human-like interactions.

The proposed computational model is applied in the context of school bullying. Bullying is a prevalent issue that affects the well-being and social dynamics within educational environments. By applying ToM principles to the development of socio-cognitive agents, this research aims to provide insights into how these agents can detect, prevent, and address instances of bullying. Supporting the proposed model with social theories further enhances its credibility and applicability to real-world scenarios. Moreover, this study sets the stage for future work that will implement the multi-agent system to demonstrate its functionality and effectiveness in combating bullying incidents.

This work is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a background about the main concepts used in this work. Section 3 reviews related works concerning the combination of both approaches. Section 4 presents the proposed computational model that integrates ToM with BDI architecture. Section 5 proposes an application of the model in a case study of a bullying scenario. Finally, Section 6 outlines some conclusions and future work.

2 Background

2.1 Theory of Mind (ToM)

The well-known Theory of Mind (ToM) defines a fundamental ability in social interaction that refers to the cognitive ability to attribute mental states, such as *beliefs*, *desires*, *intentions*, and emotions, to oneself and others in order to understand and predict behavior [18]. ToM allows individuals to navigate complex social interactions and relationships, and is crucial for human social cognition. This ability begins to develop in the early stages of childhood, being aware that people’s knowledge, beliefs, and goals are different from our own. For example, by observing John examining the contents of the refrigerator, we might infer that “John is hungry.” Consequently, we might get up and offer him some food. The cognitive ability to empathize with and comprehend the perspectives of others confers a substantial evolutionary advantage to humans. This capacity enhances the adaptive interactions with the environment and fosters more effective cooperation and social cohesion among individuals [9]. This understanding enables

individuals to navigate intricate social dynamics, foster mutual comprehension, and enhance collective well-being.

One critical aspect of ToM is the ability to recognize that other people may hold beliefs that differ from our own. This is known as the “false-belief” test, such as the Sally-Anne task, and is commonly used to evaluate ToM in children in different age ranges [2]. In the false-belief test, a child is presented with a story in which a character holds a false belief about a situation, and the child is then asked to predict how the character will behave.

The interplay between ToM and context-awareness is of paramount importance for the strategic modeling of an opponent. The consideration of contextual information becomes crucial in resolving uncertainties about plausible mental states of others. By taking into account the situational factors and the context in which individuals’ thoughts, beliefs, and intentions unfold, one can better understand and predict their behavior. This contextual understanding enhances the accuracy of mental state attributions, allowing for more effective interaction and decision-making in social and strategic settings.

Two prominent theories have emerged to attempt to explain ToM: **Theory-Theory** (TT) and **Simulation Theory** (ST) (*Sec. 4*). These theories aim to elucidate the process by which individuals perceive and interpret the mental states of others. According to TT, individuals construct explicit theories about the minds of others based on observations and inferences [10]. On the other hand, ST posits that individuals simulate the mental states of others by adopting their perspectives and matching them with own mental states [13]. These concepts, by allowing a better understanding of the mental states of others, could prevent complex social situations such as **bullying** (*Sec. 5*) or facilitate interactions between people with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) or Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD).

2.2 BDI Agent Architecture

Belief-Desire-Intention (BDI) models have been widely used for Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) to model the reasoning of agents that interact in an environment with other agents. These models provide a natural way to represent an agent’s beliefs, desires, and intentions, which are essential for making decisions and executing actions in a dynamic and uncertain world [19]. In a BDI model, an agent’s beliefs represent its knowledge about the world, desires represent its goals or preferences, and intentions represent its plans or strategies for achieving its goals, being all of them used for its reasoning process. A typical BDI agent has a goal base, plan base, plan library, and intentions, and those form the elements of its reasoning [12]. Moreover, the BDI approach allows the integration of new functionalities, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, to raise the level of abstraction of agent programming, context sensitivity, flexible decision-making capabilities and a fruitful framework for an adaptation to new technologies [3]. Their popularity is on the rise across multiple fields, including robotics and game theory. In this work, a BDI model is used to represent and reason about mental attitudes mentioned in the previous Section.

3 Related Works

The integration of ToM into computational models has been extensively studied due to its significance for inferring beliefs, predicting behavior, and enhancing reasoning abilities. Some proposals have used different techniques such as Bayesian-ToM in a partially observable Markov decision process (POMDPs), Reinforcement Learning (RL), Inverse Reinforcement Learning (IRL), and MAS [9]. Although these techniques still have limitations, it is notable that they have potential for developing intelligent systems that model complex behaviors of human mind.

One of such ToM integration approaches is that using MAS and BDI model to enhance agents' social behavior capabilities. For instance, Bose et al. [6] have developed a formal model based on BDI concepts to evaluate an agent's reasoning about another agent's reasoning process. This proposal focuses on these concepts at two different levels of architecture. The first one uses BDI concepts within ToM to describe the reasoning of agents, while the second one uses these concepts to describe the metareasoning of one agent about the other agent. It does this using a high-level modeling language called LEADSTO, which describes dynamics in terms of direct temporal dependencies between state properties in successive states. This model has been evaluated in a case study on social manipulation, animal behavior and social anticipation [4,5].

Another proposal discusses the challenges of developing social non-player characters (NPCs) and highlights the importance of a model for character decision making in games [23]. A BDI model is proposed for implementing socially-aware characters based on ToM. Another article describes ToM agents relying on a combination of theory-theory (TT) and simulation theory (ST) [11]. The approach is illustrated as a virtual training system and the goal is to develop agents with a believable social behavior and provide a reasoning about their behavior. A later study compared agents without a ToM, TT-ToM agents with ST-ToM agents [12]. The results revealed that ToM agents outperformed non-ToM agents and that models using ST represent ToM better than TT models.

Recently, a cognitive model has been proposed that enables a robot to regulate its level of collaborative autonomy by integrating Delegation Theory, ToM, and BDI [7]. This decision-making system, implemented using the JaCaMo framework, enables the robot to effectively manage collaborative conflicts and adapt its social autonomy. Another proposal presents a formal semantics for using ToM in agent communication, using the BDI elements (beliefs, desires, intentions, plans) that are applicable with agent-oriented programming languages [16]. Later, this proposal was expanded for providing the agents' with capabilities for uncertainty considerations [22]. They also proposed a high-level approach for modeling deception in MAS using ToM principles, integrating elements from *Interpersonal Deception Theory* and *Information Manipulation Theory 2* to capture the dynamics between agents [21]. The results indicate that unintended deception can arise from certain agent dynamics.

Another proposal presents an algorithm that jointly infers mental states, and action schemas of a BDI agent by maximizing the rationality contained in ob-

servations [17]. They evaluated this algorithm on Planning Domain Description Language (PDDL) domains, and constructed a possible probability distribution of plans and observations for actor’s model using prior assumptions, beliefs, and observations as evidence. Additionally, a ToM architecture for joint human-robot activities was proposed, which involves mediating joint activities (who will do what) through dialogue to specify commitments between human agent and the robot [24]. The proposed architecture was formalized and illustrated in a scenario where a human and a robot mediate the task of bringing the human medications.

The integration of ToM and BDI models has attracted significant attention in the pursuit of more intelligent and socially adept systems. This integration holds great promise for enhancing system effectiveness and enabling seamless integration with advanced technologies. However, some challenges have been identified, such as the absence of an architecture that correctly represents the ToM, replanning of actions, robustness in reasoning deviations, among others. This paper proposes to tackle the initial challenge by introducing a robust architectural framework that proficiently amalgamates and defines the internal ToM process.

4 Integrating Theory of Mind with the BDI Approach

The integration of ToM with the BDI approach in a computational model offers a promising opportunity to improve the capabilities of agent systems in understanding, simulating, representing and attributing the mental states of others. Within the BDI framework, different elements of ToM can be effectively incorporated, allowing agents to simulate and attribute mental states to other agents. For this reason, in this work an architecture that integrates ToM and BDI is presented to provide agents such facilities. Figure 1 depicts how this architecture adapts the BDI-approach including a *Theory of Mind Processing* component. As this Figure illustrates, the architecture enables the interplay between the key components of BDI and the cognitive processes associated with ToM, highlighting how these elements contribute to agents’ enhanced ability to simulate, infer, and reason about the beliefs, desires, and intentions of their counterparts. Following, the elements that make up the architecture are presented:

- **Mental State:** This definition plays a fundamental role within the framework of ToM. It refers to internal representations of cognitive and emotional processes occurring in an individual’s mind. Mental states attributed to other agents are conceived as unobservable, theoretical assumptions invoked to explain and predict behavior. In order to represent such Mental State, the BDI approach has been used as follows:
 - **Beliefs:** In ToM, beliefs are fundamental for comprehending the perspectives and expectations of others. To incorporate this concept into the BDI approach, agents maintain a belief base that includes not only their own beliefs but also beliefs attributed to other agents. This enables agents to reason about the mental states of others and anticipate their behaviors based on their beliefs.

Fig. 1: The general BDI-ToM architecture

- Desires and Intentions:** ToM recognizes desires and intentions as essential components for understanding the actions of others. BDI agents can address such understanding by having their own desires and intentions, as well as attributing mental states to other agents. This integration allows agents to better grasp the motivations and goals driving the behaviors of other agents, leading to more accurate modeling and decision-making.
- Theory of Mind Processing component:** The process of ToM is dynamic and involves revision as new information is acquired. This reflects a learning process that occurs through interactions between the mind and the environment. Theory-Theory (TT) and Simulation-Theory (ST) have been proposed for explaining ToM [1]. The integration of ToM and BDI paves the way for a more comprehensive understanding of how agents can model and interact with the mental states of others. For this reason, it is important to detail how the *Theory of Mind Processing* component can attribute mental states to support ToM. This component combines ST and TT in order to create a *hybrid model* in the processing component, aimed at obtaining a more comprehensive representation of the mental states of other agents. The general process is outlined in Algorithm 1 and is described as follows:
 - Theory-Theory.** This explains that understanding other minds involves constructing an explicit symbolic theory with axioms and inference rules [10] where mental states are represented as inferred constructs derived from a naive theory. Through observation, and focusing on the behaviors of others, individuals are able to infer their possible mental states. Therefore, as Algorithm 1 states, TT uses cognitive theories and social behavioral knowledge, also incorporating the perceptions of the context

and the initial beliefs of the agent, to generate possible mental states attributed to the other agents. As perceiving the context is an important part of the model, it is proposed to use a *Processing Function* as a context-aware system under the characteristics of an AmI system to obtain this context information [20].

- **Simulation-Theory.** It proposes that individuals simulate the mental states of others by using their own thoughts and feelings as models. They strive to *infer*, within their mental state, and *perspectives* of others, enabling them to better understand those mental states and consider them when making decisions. ST suggests that this is possible by adopting their perspective, tracking or matching their states with *resonant states* of one’s own, being the later simulated mental states experienced by an observer while attempting to understand the mental states of another individual. This simulation process facilitates *empathy* and understanding of others’ behaviors in terms of their own mental states and enhances the agents’ ability to infer the intentions behind others’ actions and react appropriately. Subsequently, as Algorithm 1 depicts, the output of TT acts as input for ST, which simulates, empathizes, and infers the definitive mental states of the agents. These inferred mental states are evaluated and then integrated into the agent’s beliefs, ultimately updating their mental state.
- **Consistency Verification.** It validates the coherence of the generated mental states with observed sensory input and contextual cues, assessing their alignment with the goals of the agent using predefined parameters. It iterates to refine simulations and adjusts mental states if inconsistencies are detected. Otherwise, the generated mental states become definitive and are incorporated into agent’s beliefs.
- **Decision-Making Component:** The agent’s mental state, updated through inference of other agents’ mental states carried out by the *Theory of Mind Processing* component, is integrated into a planning and execution mechanism. This mechanism employs system goals and a utility function to determine the actions or sub-goals necessary for goal satisfaction.

5 Case Study: Bullying Scenario

The following case study showcases the practical application of the presented architecture in the context of bullying, emphasizing its relationship with ToM. It has been detected that “pure” bullies exhibit advanced ToM skills, allowing them to effectively plan and execute their actions, or conversely, victims of bullying may exhibit deficits in these skills which perpetuates the cycle of victimization [14]. Therefore, applying ToM as an approach is viable to understand the bullying process and gain insights into how children perceive the behavior of individuals involved in the case study.

For developing this case study, the **Prometheus Methodology** [15], was used for designing a MAS for bullying intervention, as this methodology enables

Algorithm 1: Theory of Mind Processing component

Input : Agent's own Beliefs and Percepts
Output: Beliefs, desires, and intentions to the other agents based on the inferred mental states.

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begin
  TT Subprocess:
    Inputs: context percepts, initial beliefs of the agent, cognitive theories, and knowledge about social behaviors.
    Output: temporary mental states of other agents.
  ST Subprocess:
  while mental states are not consistent do
    - Internal Simulation Section;
      Inputs: temporary mental states from TT subprocess;
      Output: perspectives and emotions simulated.
    - Empathy Section:
      Inputs: internal information from other agents.
      Output: empathetic understanding of the mental states.
    - Inference Section:
      Inputs: understanding of TT's mental states.
      Output: refined possible mental states of other agents.
    - Consistency Evaluation:
      Inputs: mental states of other agents.
      Output: evaluation of consistency.
  return Inferred Mental States

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the development of socio-cognitive agents. It has been adapted for providing such agents with ToM capabilities, enhancing their ability to address bullying incidents effectively. The case study revolves around a bullying incident involving the teacher and student agents. It highlights the importance of timely intervention and a safe environment. It is also described how, by integrating the BDI and ToM framework, the student agent understands their own mental states, and empathizes with the victim. This allows for assessment, intent to help, and decision making that leads to teacher intervention and victim support. Due to the limited space constraints, some design details have been omitted in this paper.

5.1 System Specification

According to Prometheus, the first step is to identify the main goals of the MAS to capture the interactions and behaviors of its different agents. For this case study, the primary goals are to detect bullying and implementing interventions to mitigate their occurrence (Fig. 2). This ultimately aims to improve the understanding of the underlying mechanisms of bullying and contribute to the development of effective prevention and intervention strategies. Then, once the goals were identified, the *Context* of the MAS was defined as follows:

- A school setting with multiple classrooms, a playground, and common areas.
- Students with different backgrounds interacting in social groups.

5.2 Architectural Design

The *Agents* that make up the MAS were identified during this phase. One of the agent types is *Student* that may play ‘Victim’, ‘Bully’, and ‘Observer’ roles. The other agent type is *Teacher* who plays ‘Intervener’ role (Fig. 3). An explanation of the roles of the agents and their actions is detailed in Table 1. In the following, the computational model for the student agent with the role of Observer (Fig. 4) is designed. This agent perceives the behavior of other agents and, once understands their motivations, chooses its future actions based on the defined goals.

Table 1: Roles and actions

Role	Description	Actions
Victim (V)	A student who may become a target of bullying.	Participates in school activities, interacts with peers, and responds to the behaviors of others.
Bully (B)	A student engaging in bullying behaviors.	Displays aggressive behaviors such as teasing, physical intimidation, exclusion, or spreading rumors.
Observer (O)	An agent with a role in perceiving bullying incidents.	Observes social interactions, monitors V and B behaviors, and notifies when bullying is perceived to be occurring.
Intervener (I)	An agent responsible for addressing bullying incidents.	Receives notification from the O and intervenes when necessary to address bullying and provide support to the V.

5.3 Detailed Design

In this phase it is important to define the capabilities of the agents and the actions for their assigned roles. For this reason, the *Capability Overview* and the *ToM Processing Component* were defined as detailed next.

Fig. 2: Main Goals of the system

Fig. 3: Assignment of roles to agents of the MAS

Fig. 4: Overview of the Agent with Observer Role

Capability Overview. It defines the plans and actions of the agents using the BDI architecture. For the bullying case study, it was defined as follows:

- Student Bully approaches Victim student, and starts verbally harassing or physically intimidating them.
- Victim student, feeling targeted and threatened, responds with signs of distress or attempts to defend themselves.
- Observer student, with *ToM Processing Component* capabilities, notices the interaction between Victim and Bully students.
- Applying ToM, Observer student understands that Victim student is experiencing distress due to the bullying behavior of Bully student.
- Observer student empathizes with Victim student, recognizing their perspectives and updates their own beliefs and desires about the situation.
- Based on the inferred mental states, Observer decides the appropriate interventions to address the bullying through a decision-making component to fulfill the simulation goals.
- Observer interprets and empathizes with Bully’s behavior, addressing the issue while supporting Victim and reporting incidents to teacher agent when needed.

ToM Processing Component. This component is part of the capabilities of Observer, which runs the TT and ST subprocesses to detect bullying. In the following the subprocesses that made it up, as well their inputs and output, are detailed for the bullying case study:

1. $TT_subprocess(Percepts, Beliefs, Cognitive\ Theories) \rightarrow Mental_states_temp$
 - **Input:** *Percepts*: Sensory information, including observable behaviors of Victim and Bully. *Beliefs*: Initial beliefs about Victim and Bully’s backgrounds and attitudes. *Cognitive Theories*: Behavior patterns based on cognitive theories.
 - **Output:** Generate temporal Mental States for Victim and Bully, such as beliefs, intentions, and emotions.
2. $ST_subprocess(Mental_states_temp) \rightarrow Inferred_Mental_States$
 - **Input:** Receive the output of the TT subprocess including temporary mental states for Victim and Bully.
 - **Output:** Infer Mental States by:
 - Simulating the perspectives of Victim and Bully within Observer’s mental state.
 - Empathizing with Victim and Bully by mentally adopting their perspectives and experiencing resonant states.
 - Understanding the reasons why Agent Bully is bullying and why Agent Victim is susceptible to being bullied.

6 Conclusions

In conclusion, this work has demonstrated the potential of incorporating ToM into MAS for supporting social-aware AmI environments. The computational model presented in this study successfully applies the principles of ToM and the BDI agent model to develop socio-cognitive agents capable of reasoning and decision-making in real-world scenarios. The case study focused on bullying has shown the possibility of incorporating this computational model to promote social behaviors with the aim of reducing the presence of this problem in schools.

Moreover, as part of our future work, the integration of ToM and the BDI approach presented in this study will be implemented in a modeling and simulation framework for creating explicit agent-based simulations to demonstrate its functionality and effectiveness. This is important for researching and comparing the behavior of agents who do or do not have a ToM. These areas present exciting opportunities for advancing the capabilities of socio-cognitive agents and enhancing their social interaction and understanding, which would contribute to the development of more sophisticated and social-aware Ambient Intelligent systems, enabling them to effectively navigate and participate in various social contexts with human-like reasoning and decision-making abilities.

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